
Educating young social innovators from 6 to 16 in makerspace settings: Case studies of existing approaches and their implications for the European initiative DOIT

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Abstract: Educating young social innovators in makerspaces – children and youth – are the main idea of the DOIT initiative “DOIT- Entrepreneurial skills for young social innovators in an open digital world“ (2017-2020) co-financed by the European Union. Although this is an innovative approach, especially in the DOIT’s special context to develop a new early entrepreneurship education, there are already several initiatives doing similar since some years. Within this contribution, we will therefore systematically analyse four of these existing projects and their approaches of educating young social innovators in the special setting of makerspaces, where a usage of digital technologies or traditional tools as well as the development of prototypes and objects like machines or applications are the result. The case studies analysis will use project descriptions and expert interviews with the relevant people and describe the activities according to a common scheme.

1 INTRODUCTION

Children and youth between 6 to 16 years are the addressed target group of the Horizon 2020 project “DOIT- Entrepreneurial skills for young social innovators in an open digital world“ (2017-2020) co-financed by the European Union (Schön et al., 2018). It builds upon the consideration that social innovations in makerspace settings allow authentic learning experiences fostering future entrepreneurial spirit and ambition to co-create a (better) world. The DOIT initiative refers and builds upon the experiences of social entrepreneurship and innovation education for young learners and maker education (see Schön et al., 2017, Hornung-Prähäuser et al., 2018, see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Five dimensions of DOIT's learning approach

Source: Schön et al., 2017, Schön et al., 2018

DOIT aims to develop and test this special approach and publish the tested activities within so-called toolboxes for children as well for potential facilitators of projects. Therefore we try to consolidate as well existing approaches.

Within this contribution, we will systematically analyze four existing approaches of educating young social innovators in the special setting of makerspaces, where the usage of digital technologies or traditional tools as well as the development of prototypes and objects like machines or applications are the result. Four projects from German-speaking Europe will be described and compared as case studies with a common structure, building upon project descriptions and expert interviews. The cases will be shortly described and compared concerning general implications for future projects, for example the DOIT initiative. To start with, we will give a short introduction into social innovation education, maker education and early entrepreneurship education.

2 SOCIAL INNOVATION EDUCATION, MAKER EDUCATION AND EARLY ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

Within the following paragraphs, we want to give a short introduction into social innovation education, maker education as well as early entrepreneurship education.

To start with, social innovation education is the idea to train and educate future social innovators. These people develop solutions to meet social needs and solve societal problems, so-called social innovations, which includes products as well as new processes. A hallmark of social innovations is the need to get them accepted by the impacted social groups, which need to participate to overcome a specific social challenge (Hochgerner, 2012). Not directly addressing social innovation, so-called “design thinking” activities are nevertheless often used within social innovation development and education.

Maker education follows the idea to learn and teach within makerspaces, which are collaborative spaces for innovative forms of production and digital do-it-yourself work. Within this learning and teaching approach concrete or virtual products are developed, constructed and/or done by oneself or in collaboration with others using not always, but eventually also, digital tools provided in a makerspace (Schön, Ebner & Kumar, 2014). Making as a constructionist activity is a theoretically and historically founded principle for successful learning, coined as “learning by making (doing)” (Papert & Harel, 1991). A makerspace learning setting will typically (though not exclusively) focus on digital fabrication, where children are allowed to choose tools as well as other resources (Schön et al., 2017).

Lackéus (2015) provides an overview of the wide variety of “early entrepreneurship education” and differences in the meaning and learning goals and approaches in the diverse European countries. He suggests the term “entrepreneurial education” for approaches that focus on children’s skills and interests that give them the opportunity to shape the (future) world. (Early) entrepreneurship education in Europe can be seen as “measure to enable future civilians to shape society, societal processes and developments” (Schön et al., 2017).

3 GOOD PRACTICES: FOUR CASES FROM GERMAN SPEAKING EUROPE

The following case studies analysis use project descriptions and expert interviews (in July 2018) with the relevant people and describe the activities according to a scheme that focus on (a) general description of background and ambitions, (b) structure and time plan of the project (c) role of social innovation and its support in the project, (d)

role of making and makerspace settings, (e) implementation in current education, (f) results and lessons learned. The analysis comprises the following initiatives from German-speaking Europe: Jugend hackt (DE/AT/CH, hackathons for a better world for children from 12 to 18), WILMA in Lustenau (AT, children were developing prototypes addressing UN sustainability goals), Baut Eure Zukunft (DE, social innovation through design thinking for schools), Make Your School (DE, maker projects to enhance the school). The projects were selected because they can build upon broad experiences and all provide information and materials, such as handbooks.

3.1 Case Study A: Make Your School - Eure Ideenwerkstatt

Name of the project	Make Your School
Involved organisations and fundings	Initiated and organised by: Wissenschaft im Dialog www.wissenschaft-im-dialog.de Supported by: Klaus-Tschira Stiftung www.klaus-tschira-stiftung.de
Experiences (number of involved children, evaluation)	In the pilot phase (school year 2016/2017), the format was tested in five schools throughout Germany. Because of positive responses the number of workshops increased to nine in 2017/2018. In 2018/2019, 26 Hackdays will take place. Per Hackday event 25 to 50 children from the 8th grade upwards take part.
The approach in one sentence	In extracurricular events, children from the 8th grade upwards are encouraged to develop ideas to improve and co-design their school environment with the assistance of digital and technical tools.
Available materials	Handbook: http://www.makeyourschool.de/wp-content/uploads/MYS_Handbuch_DIGITAL.pdf Toolkit: http://www.makeyourschool.de/koffer/
Sources for case study	Website: http://www.makeyourschool.de/ Resources (Literature): Make Your School Handbook http://www.makeyourschool.de/wp-content/uploads/MYS_Handbuch_DIGITAL.pdf Interview with Laura Krauß (project manager at Make Your School) At the end of September the second edition of the manual will be published and a new website will go online. The URL www.makeyourschool.de remains unchanged.

3.1.1 General description of background and ambitions

The project was initiated in the year 2016 by “*Wissenschaft im Dialog*” - An initiative of Germany’s scientific community and is supported by the Klaus Tschira Stiftung. During so-called “hackdays”, which are organized by the project, children from the 8th grade upwards are encouraged to think about ideas to improve and co-design their school environment with the assistance of digital and technical tools. The hackdays are extracurricular events that take place in schools for two to three days. Through teamwork, children can learn from each other’s creativity, programming or design skills. The heterogeneity of school children allows a wide variety of skills to be incorporated into group work. Make Your School provides the technical, digital and making tools for the youth to implement their ideas. Additionally, specially developed workshop materials as well as mentors with technical and design competences support the idea finding process. Through the technical and digital tools the children are also easily introduced to programming. By acquiring problem-solving and application skills and working closely together as a team, they learn additional working methods that strengthen their awareness of the fact that they can actively participate in shaping and making a difference together.

3.1.2 Structure and time plan of the project

The structure of the event is split in three phases: preparation, work and follow-up (“make it start, make it happen, make it last”). According to the handbook, the planning of the action should be started at least 12 weeks in advance. Organisational and administrative issues are handled (e.g. rooms, responsible persons, times, experts, catering). All materials, mentors and also the catering are paid by Make Your School. The working phase includes the actual hackdays (two to three days). Mentors explain the process and the topic, then the children start with the idea generating and team building. Each project school gets toolkits with material and also a budget for additionally needed materials. Then the actual hacking phase begins. Mentors are available if questions arise. They support the students to take the challenges and solve problems by themselves. During the event the teachers still hold the supervisory role, but do not actively intervene in the hacking process. Within the working phase, the teams also present their prototypes and ideas. The follow-up phase then deals with the sustainability of the projects. The aim of Make Your School is to support teamwork, problem-solving skills, and the ability to work independently. Moreover, it is desirable, yet no condition to participation, to implement the prototypes and ideas of the children as far as possible with the help of local supporters. A detailed time description of all tasks can be found in the handbook.

3.1.3 Role of social innovation and its support in the project

The children are motivated to actively participate in shaping their environment. The process in which this happens is based on the social innovation spiral (see Murray et

al., 2010). The children are promptly given the task of actively shaping their school environment and thus finding solutions to problems. The idea generation phase is followed by a prototyping phase (the actual hacking). Afterwards, the prototypes and ideas are presented and the plenum is encouraged to ask questions about the ideas. Make Your School pursues the idea that students continue to work on their hacks after the actual event, e.g. in working group formats, in local makerspaces or in youth research projects. Of course, ideas are also welcome where no continuation or sustainable development is possible from the outset. The focus is on trial and error.

3.1.4 Role of making and makerspace setting

The project aims to break through regular school lessons and create a creative atmosphere with open learning environments. Unusual and creative ideas and implementation possibilities are allowed and wanted during the Hackdays. In this open setting, students have the opportunity to also implement ideas which seemed unconventional at first glance. There are no evaluations or classifications of ideas - neither during nor after the event. All ideas are equally welcome. In the foreground of the open workshop atmosphere is the independent planning and implementation of the hacks in the team. The young people must develop and define task packages independently and assign them to team members. It quickly becomes clear that all competencies are needed in the team. How the time is scheduled is left to the participants. You decide yourself how much time you spend on which task (e.g. break times are chosen by yourself). It is also up to the young people to choose the materials for the hacking and they have to become creative when certain materials are not available. Previous knowledge is not necessary for the Make Your School Hackdays. Even if the students had no access to programming and hacking in advance, they are able to obtain information about the actuators, sensors and microcontrollers independently via tutorials - the focus is on trying them out. In this way, they can acquire the learning content independently and without the need for teachers. The open setting also creates the difficulty that the motivation must come from the young people. Without own motivation there is no result. During the event, no one prescribes which tasks are to be completed in which time, so the students must define and implement tasks of their own accord.

3.1.5 Implementation in current education

Through the open setting of the hackdays the project aims to break up the standardized school routine. The continuation of such hacker activities by makerdays or working groups at school is desired by the project. For the duration of the project, students and teachers must be exempt from regular lessons, which is why the implementation of the project in normal school life represents an organisational challenge for teachers. Alternatively, the format can be offered in fixed project weeks of the school.

It turns out that all schools that already held hackdays in the 2017/2018 school year will continue to organize hackdays in the coming school year. Therefore Make Your School becomes an integral part of the school year and establishes itself as a school offer. The conviction of the school management, which submits an application as a project school every school year, is a relevant part in this. Schools that have already organized hackdays can participate in the project every year. This offer is accepted by the majority of schools, which shows that the participating schools generally regard a long-term implementation of the project in everyday school life as desirable. However, it is only conditionally possible for a school to carry out the project independently, as the provision of the mentors and the extensive material cases by the project team is essential.

3.1.6 Results and lessons learned

A total of 20 hackdays were planned for the 2018/2019 school year (ten schools from previous years plus ten new project schools). Due to the great positive response, Make Your School decided together with the Klaus Tschira Foundation to increase the number to 26 in order to be able to include more schools in the project. Hackdays events take place in 12 out of 16 German states. There is still a great demand from schools to participate in the project. It is particularly worth mentioning that all schools from the past project years are participating again, since, among others, pupils from other years explicitly asked to be allowed to participate in the coming year.

Based on the first results of the empirical accompanying research of the TU Braunschweig it can already be stated that there is a connection between gender and the technical/informatics previous knowledge, so that participating schoolgirls indicate on average less interest in computer science topics in advance. However, there is no longer any connection between gender and the fun of hackdays through evaluation directly after hackdays. This shows that both pupils are supported and addressed by this project in connection with technical and informatics topics. To sum up: More girls were little or not at all interested in computer science at the beginning. After the hackdays, however, all participants, regardless of gender, rated the fun of hacking as equally positive.

3.2 Case Study B: Baut Eure Zukunft

Name of the project	Baut Eure Zukunft
Involved organisations and fundings	Baut Eure Zukunft is a joint initiative of Social Impact (https://socialimpact.eu/), Deutsche Bank (https://www.deutsche-bank.de/pk.html) and Deutsche Bank Stiftung (https://www.deutsche-bank-stiftung.de/)
Experiences (number of involved children)	So far 46 projects have been published (as of July 30, 2018).

dren, evaluation)	
Available materials	Toolboxes (open topic, mobbing, poverty, violence and anxiety of the future) for download on website
The approach in one sentence	It is a six-hour teaching concept for schools or youth facilities, focusing on tackling problems in the in the everyday school life of young people (e.g. mobbing, violence, bullying) with the help of a digital toolbox with instructions.
Sources for case study	Website: https://baut-eure-zukunft.eu Toolboxes/Handbook (download on website)

3.2.1 General description of background and ambitions

The project *Baut Eure Zukunft* started in 2017 and is a joint initiative of *Social Impact*, *Deutsche Bank Stiftung* and *Deutsche Bank*. The aim of the project is that participating children are learning to face everyday challenges like mobbing, poverty, violence or anxiety about the future and learn how to manage them successfully. Furthermore the project can help children to strengthen their empathy towards others as well as their social and collaborative competences. The concept is based on the model of design thinking and consists of seven phases. In the first phase the children learn about the used method in a video. They also build the teams, set the rules and build a creative workspace. The aim of the second phase is to understand the challenge by doing some research for the topic and working with the given informational materials. Further on the groups are taking interviews with a person who is affected by a certain problem so they can build up empathy and get a better understanding of the problem. In the fourth phase the results of the interviews are evaluated and in the fifth phase ideas for possible solutions are developed. In the next phase the groups are making prototypes to present their solutions. In the seventh and final phase the groups present their prototypes and can upload their solution at the website.

3.2.2 Structure and time plan of the project

The toolbox offers a six-hour-long (three times 90 min) concept that teachers can use in their class, containing a schedule, texts, videos, worksheets, and background information to three different topics. In the first double lesson the children are going through the first three phases. They build teams, search for information and prepare everything for the interviews. As homework they have to make an interview. The next double lesson contains the phases four to six where the teams are talking about the interviews they made and decide for what aspect they want to find a solution. The collect ideas and then start prototyping. In the last double lesson the team present their ideas and concepts and after the presentation and the given feedback they can

improve their prototype and can upload their idea if they want to apply for the competition. The last minutes are for a final reflection of the project.

There is also a two-day competition that takes place in the summer vacations every year, where a jury invites up to ten teams who have applied for the competition to Berlin. At the competition the teams can show what they have learned and can present their ideas and prototypes regarding the announced topic. The topics are based on the 17 UN Global Goals whereas the exact challenge is announced at the beginning of the competition in Berlin.

3.2.3 Role of social innovation and its support

Baut Eure Zukunft is based on the Method of design thinking and the teachers are guiding the children with help of the materials in the toolbox through the seven phases that were described above. During this process the children get aware of problems in their environment and learn how to face and find solutions for them.

At the competition the teams get in contact with the 17 global goals for sustainable development and have to find - just like they did at school - solutions for the problems. While the teams are going through the design thinking process they get support from mentors.

3.2.4 Role of making and makerspace setting

The project encourages the children to work in an action-oriented way. Already in the beginning of the process a creative workplace for all the groups is made. Later on when the phase of prototyping begins, the children are free to design and construct the prototype, as they like, using all kinds of materials in every creative and possible way. Especially at the competition in Berlin the teams have a lot of possibilities since the creative workplace is provided by the organisers whereas at school the groups may have limited possibilities to create a creative workspace or don't have such a variety of available materials.

3.2.5 Implementation in current education

Schools contribute a lot to the development of key competencies the children need for their future, but teachers are often limited by curricula and fixed patterns in teaching design. "In addition, there is a lack of time resources to focus teaching on the individual strengths and weaknesses of the children or to develop new pedagogical concepts." (see enorm magazin, 2018). The format adapts to everyday school life by being integrated into it. For three double lessons (three times 90 minutes), the pupils can ride out on their projects and go through the seven phases that have already been described.

3.2.6 Results and lessons learned

Everyone who downloads and uses the toolbox has the possibility to upload his or her project on the homepage. So far 46 projects have been published (as of July 30, 2018).

3.3 Case Study C: Jugend hackt

Name of the project	Jugend hackt - mit Code die Welt verbessern (“improve the world with code”)
Involved organisations and fundings	Jugend hackt is a program of medialepfade.org (https://medialepfade.org/) and the Open Knowledge Foundation Germany (https://okfn.de/),
Experiences (number of involved children, evaluation)	By July 2018, 28 hackathons have already been organized by Jugend hackt. In total, more than 700 participants were reached, resulting in 275 projects.
The approach in one sentence	Under the motto “Code for a better world”, children from 12 to 18 develop projects tackling socially relevant issues in hackathons.
Available material	Hackathon handbook, self-study materials: https://jugendhackt.org/material/
Sources for case study	Website: https://jugendhackt.org/ Youtube Channel: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZPARo7O1Y07hK1L-JfvUw Resources (Literature) Hackathon handbook: https://jugendhackt.org/material/ Scientific evaluation: https://jugendhackt.org/files/2016/03/jugend-hackt-2015-Evaluationsbericht.pdf Interview with Robert Alisch

3.3.1 General description of background and ambitions

Since 2013, the project is organised by the *Open Knowledge Foundation* and *Medialepfade.org*. With the help of voluntary mentors, young people are working on their ideas for a better world under the motto *Improve the world with code*. *Jugend hackt* uses the hackathon format. Hackathons are characterized by their clear formatting and product orientation: Interdisciplinary teams work on specific products within a fixed period of time. The goal at the end of the hackathon is to present an executable software and/or hardware hack or at least a prototype that deals with a social problem.

3.3.2 Structure and time plan of the project

As described above, hackathons are used as a format. The workshop is held over three days (mostly weekends). During the hackathon, creative and useful software and/or hardware solutions are to be developed for a fixed period of time. *Jugend hackt* works with open data. “Open means anyone can freely access, use, modify, and share for any

purpose (subject, at most, to requirements that preserve provenance and openness).” (see Open Definition). The course of the event consists of an introduction with inputs to relevant topics, brainstorming for ideas, formation of groups, prototyping with code and ends with a presentation of the developed software and/or hardware prototypes. The first day of the event is intended for an introduction to the topic, inputs and brainstorming. On the second day the groups are formed and the whole day is planned for coding and prototyping. The third day is used to prepare and finalize the prototypes for the (public) presentation.

In the course of the hackathon, the intensity of the support decreases more and more, the young people are supposed to manage the time and distribute the work in the group by themselves. Mentors are always available when problems arise. To ensure that young people can work well during the prototyping phase, the open data to be worked with must be processed in a machine-readable format. This must be ensured by the organizers before the hackathon begins. Parallel to the prototyping process, so-called Lightning Talks are offered. This is a series of workshops and lectures - in 15-minute sessions, various topics are presented that can be interesting beyond group work.

3.3.3 Role of social innovation and its support

Hackathons can be used to relate to the lives of young people. The thematic orientation can only take place in accordance with the description of the target group in order to produce a sustainable concept. In this way, content focuses are identified which actually follow the interest of the young people. In the best case, the target group is involved in the decision process in advance to ensure that the participants are actually interested in the event and want to participate.

In the case of *Jugend hackt*, the participants can weight their learning goals according to their personal interest. Stickers on the participants' backs signal to the mentors which learning content is important to the young people during the event. Participants can choose between "expanding technical skills", "networking with others", "improving the world" and "learning more about open data". At the same time, the technical solution to these questions creates experiences of self-efficacy. Thus a positive access to technology is created, which serves not only the end in itself of the pure understanding of technology. Through access to open data, young people can deal with problems at the level of civil society and thus get the feeling that they can make a difference in the world. The core concern of *Jugend hackt* is not only to strengthen the participants' technical skills, but also to sensitize them to the socio-political dimension of these skills.

3.3.4 Role of making and makerspace setting

The open setting of *Jugend hackt* is intentionally designed in this way and usually differs only slightly in the spatial possibilities of the event location. The working groups

can freely choose their places for the work on the projects. The close proximity of the different working groups strengthens the exchange on the one hand, and on the other hand also results in normal group (negotiation) processes. Furthermore, the atmosphere of the setting strengthens the feeling of solidarity, the community feeling and the sense of being able to improve the world together. Further advantages of this setting are that the mentors can look after and support several groups with their expertise at the same time and also the participants can help each other with their knowledge. With the makerspace offer on site with 3D printers, laser cutters, soldering stations, microcontrollers, sensors, VR glasses and further accessories, *Jugend hackt* supports the young people with a variety of technology and extended possibilities. They are introduced to new hardware and integrate it into project development and implementation.

3.3.5 Implementation in current education

Jugend hackt is an extracurricular support program and the normal events in the form of youth hackathons are clearly located outside of school. There is hardly any cooperation with schools.

Exceptions are the projects *Vernetzte Welten* and *Schools of Tomorrow*. At *Vernetzte Welten* in cooperation with the Goethe Institute, German children meet with students from Southeast Asia on the topic *Student Exchange of the Future*. The Asian students come from the direct school context, because they are all enrolled in schools with German lessons. The format *Schools of Tomorrow* deals with the question of how the school of tomorrow should look like. Since 2017, under the leadership of the *HKW (Haus der Kulturen der Welt)*, pupils, artists, educators and scientists include the question of how school can be shaped and how it should ideally look in the future. *Jugend hackt* accompanies schools and carries out several projects with the students. This involves, for example, virtual realities, in which the students create their new learning environments of the future with the help of VR technology. Democracy in school and participation in school has also been an exciting topic in the last edition.

3.3.6 Results and lessons learned

As already mentioned, more than 275 projects with about 700 participants have been developed over the last 28 hackathons. In 2016, the project abolished the typical hackathon competition in form of prizes for the "best" prototype. The team believes that young people face competition and pressure to perform everywhere on their path of growing up and in later life, so they wanted to take this pressure out of an event full of creativity and joint learning and creation. This also promotes cross-group exchange and peer-to-peer knowledge transfer. In order to make learning successes and desired behavior visible, Mozilla's "open badges system" was introduced and implemented at the end of 2016, with which young people can obtain eleven different badges for different social and technology skills (e.g. helping hand, open source hero). For

each badge there are exact descriptions with some criteria. The mentors and organisers of the events award the badges to the young people during the weekend. Before the online version is properly implemented, these are assigned in the form of hexagon stickers, which most young people stick on their laptops. The team's diversity efforts are already showing small successes, but still young people do not hack enough - especially girls and young people who are generally not associated with technology. New possibilities are already being worked on in this area.

3.4 Case Study D: WILMA - the inventor's workshop

Name of the project	WILMA inventor's workshop (Wir lernen durch Machen, "We Learn Through Making")
Involved organisations and fundings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops initiated by Steven Marx, supported by colleagues • Financial support by "Impulse Stiftung" (http://www.impulse-stiftung.com/) and the initiative "Tuoscht Mit?" (http://www.tuoschtmit.at/) • Mentors for WILMA are provided by local companies (e.g. Alge Elastic, Alge Electronic, Bayer Kartonagen, Blum, SIE und Walter Bösch)
Experiences (number of involved children, evaluation)	Twelve children took part in the pilot project 2017 (WILMA 1.0). With WILMA 2.0 it were already 70. They adapted the workshop according to their findings in the pilot project (see below).
The approach in one sentence	The inventors workshop WILMA encourages children from the fourth grade to give free rein to their inventive spirit and find creative solutions for problems (basing on the SDGs).
Available material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WILMA Handbook (https://w-ort.at/cms/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/WILMA_Handbuch_2018.pdf)
Sources for case study	<p>Website: https://wilmalustenau.wordpress.com/</p> <p>Resources (Literature)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.lustenau.at/de/neuigkeiten/wilma-wir-lernen-durch-machen-und-das-gemeinsam • https://www.edugroup.at/praxis/news/detail/wilma-wir-lernen-durch-machen.html • https://www.medienpaedagogik-praxis.de/2018/07/10/wir-lernen-durch-machen-ein-interview-mit-steven-marx-ueber-die-wilma-erfinderwerkstatt-in-lustenau/ • Wilma Handbook: https://w-ort.at/cms/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/WILMA_Handbuch_2018.pdf • Interview with Steven Marx

3.4.1 General description of background and ambitions

WILMA's basic idea is to encourage children to make the world a better place with realistic solutions. They should be given the space to think critically and to act as active creators of their environment. In the fast changing world of digitalization WILMA enables children to familiarize themselves with hands-on craft skills, combining these with technical and digital tools. A very important part of the concept behind WILMA is the transfer of soft skills like teamwork, problem solving, value-orientation, critical and entrepreneurial thinking and creativity. Peer support and intergenerational learning are also at the heart of this project. Children are challenged to come up with prototypes that present a solution to the problems illustrated through the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

3.4.2 Structure and time plan of the project

WILMA can be held as a one-day workshop (five double lessons, i.e. five times 90 minutes). The project team has designed the format in a way that it can be adapted as required: For example, the individual work phases can be longer so that the workshop lasts for several days. The inventor's workshop is carefully planned, but at the same time offers a lot of scope for creative thinking and making. After a general introduction, an introduction to the role of an inventor and the introduction to the SDGs, the children start to research and sketch their ideas according to the chosen goals. After this ideation phase, the participants have enough time, space and material to work on their prototypes. Mentors, apprentices and volunteers are always available to talk through the project ideas. Their role is to support the young inventors, to guide them through the problem solving, but not to present them with ready-made solutions. Among the materials available are also many recyclable materials, which can be found at home. This guarantees easy access for aspiring inventors. The largest amount of time is available for the construction of the prototype. Failure is also possible and absolutely permitted. This is one of the core principles of inventing. The last step for the children is to record a video, where they explain the functionality of their prototype and promote it.

3.4.3 Role of social innovation and its support in the project

The WILMA concept is focusing on design thinking. The mentors guide the participants through six stages: research, brainstorming, sketching, making, sharing, and reflection. By building on the SDGs, children are made aware of problems in society and encouraged to find solutions. The problems can be broken down to the local environment or thought about in a wider context, even globally. For the inventor's workshop, it is central to let the children experiment and do as much as possible independently. Basically, they should learn through their mistakes. However, this is not always possible for time or cost reasons and can also become very frustrating for the children. Here it should be paid attention to the duration and scope of the format. By

involving apprentices from local companies the children work with young, skilled people, not very much older than themselves, who can become their role models. The apprentices on the other hand swap roles from receiving instructions to teaching and leading.

3.4.4 Role of making and makerspace setting

The project promotes action-oriented digital design, which is embodied by the making concept and encourages self-directed solution-oriented action, experimentation or tinkering. These elements should combine both creative thinking on the theoretical level and the implementation of the idea in the form of a prototype on the practical level. Finally, the use of different (digital) media expands the media skills of the children as well as the respective companions and mentors. The open environment gives the children a lot of freedom to work on their ideas. Explaining analogue and digital tools to the children creates a common starting point. Whether they use them in the groups is up to them. The large selection of materials allows the design and creation of many different, creative ideas and prototypes.

3.4.5 Implementation in current education

WILMA was conducted in daily format (also possible: five double lessons) with students from the 4th grade. The format can be adapted to any age group or school level and can also be carried out outside the school context. *WILMA* is currently offered through the voluntary organisation *W*ORT* and the youth work organisation *Jugendnetzwerk SDM*, which has close links to local schools. The project is offered to schools as a project that can be integrated into the curriculum, but is carried out outside of the school building. The inventors' manual, which accompanies the project, is available as an open source document and can be downloaded for free from the *W*ORT* website. On a local level the team has close links to the council. At a regional level the necessity for such experimental spaces has just been discussed and *WILMA* was quoted as a best practice example. Contacts have been made with the politicians behind this proposal. The *WILMA* team has formed close links with IFTE (Initiative for Teaching Entrepreneurship) and the manual is now being translated into a number of languages and integrated into teacher training on an international level.

3.4.6 Results and lessons learned

The outcome from *WILMA* inventor's workshop 2018 was: "Four days + 17 global goals + 70 creative children + 12 helpful apprentices = 21 sustainable inventions for a better future!" (*W*ort*, 2018) The organisation team was overwhelmed by the creative and innovative solutions the children came up with (e.g. a plate that recognizes hunger and increases or decreases accordingly as a measure against food waste). In addition to the great interest in local companies who wanted to participate in the project and use their apprentices as mentors, intergenerational learning on site was also a

particular success. According to Steven Marx, there were also individual experiences of success: A girl who has great difficulties at school said she had a much greater desire to go to school if things were taught the way they are taught at WILMA: through creative innovative processes that are not only educational but also fun.

4 SUMMARY AND IMPLICATIONS

On the basis of the already established projects described above, statements can be made for the future that can influence projects such as DOIT and strengthen the further development of SEI. First of all, the success of the individual formats must be mentioned, which is reflected in the positive response and the associated annual increase in implementation. Each of the projects described in this paper has become an example of SEI in just a few years. Giving children the feeling of being able to change something in their environment is a predominant point in all formats and an important aspect for the future of education.

4.1 Common issues and differences of the approaches

The projects described were selected for this case study because they have the decisive aspects in common and DOIT is also integrated into this approach for social innovation and entrepreneurship education. These aspects include first and foremost the orientation towards the design thinking approach. The phases have been adapted to the context and characteristics of the respective programs. No matter how the phases were named project-specifically, the five steps are always recognizable: empathize, define, ideate, prototype and test.

Through the design thinking approach, children not only learn to work together on a topic or project, but also develop new skills on an individual level. By collaborating with others, they learn to respond to others, how to manage resources or how to use the skills of individuals to build a well-functioning team. Through the selection of topics (e.g. SDGs) the participants get to know social problems and develop empathy towards other people or groups. In the prototyping phase they learn how to deal with setbacks or celebrate success. Through this experimentation they learn a lot about the digital and technical tools, and also how they themselves can change the world with what they have. Furthermore, the projects are not only about developing these ideas and prototypes, but also about how to make them sustainable. Entrepreneurial skills are imparted not only through this sustainability aspect, but also through the final presentations or awards through competitions (as in *Baut eure Zukunft*).

These skills are taught in all projects through work in maker spaces or similar open learning environments. Depending on the provider, different quantities of analog, technical and/or digital tools are provided. Another common ground of the projects is the orientation on the sustainability goals regarding the topics to be dealt with

during the projects. In addition to the global goals, the projects also find access to problems in the environment of young people, for example by focusing on schools and their immediate environment.

In all projects, mentors, educators or other supporters are on site to help the children develop and implement their ideas and prototypes. In order to strengthen the independence and the feeling of self-efficacy of the children, the intervention on the part of the organizers is weakened further and further during the implementation. Additionally, the projects provide handbooks and toolboxes to give instructions for the implementation of such workshops.

Since the projects were selected according to their common features, it is interesting to explain in the following which differences can be detected in the individual approaches.

The first thing to mention is that the projects are carried out in different settings. *Jugend hackt* is an extracurricular event that brings together children who are enthusiastic about programming for several days. *WILMA* is also an extracurricular event, but it addresses its target group in the school context and thus generates its participants. A mixed version is *Baut Eure Zukunft*, as the workshops can be held in schools, youth facilities or by social workers. Only *Make Your School* focuses entirely on the school context in order to promote social innovations there. Especially in the area of children's education it seems to be more difficult to reach the target group outside of school - but it is still feasible, as our examples show. Here it can be said that it depends above all on the correct advertisement and announcement of such formats.

The age that is addressed in the various projects also shows small differences. While *WILMA's* target group is younger children (4th grade), *Make Your School* and *Jugend hackt* focus on young people. In the case of *Baut Eure Zukunft*, no exact age group is mentioned, but the topics mentioned also point to the use of toolboxes by young people. Two of the four projects indicate that the implementation as described in the available manuals can be adapted to any context and age group.

Furthermore, there are differences in the materials used and offered. *Baut Eure Zukunft* provides a toolbox on their homepage with instructions and copy templates on the various topics and methods. These can be downloaded by teachers, educators and social workers and edited with the children. The actual making materials are not provided by the *Baut Eure Zukunft* team, but by the schools and institutions that downloaded the toolboxes. The available resources thus shape the prototyping phase. The use of digital tools is not particularly encouraged, but there are some submitted projects on the homepage where for example video editing programs have been used. *WILMA* works with a lot of making material that can also be found at home and is suitable for prototyping (e.g. paper, cardboard, plastic). In addition, simple technical devices (soldering irons, drills) or LEDs are available. The *WILMA* organization team will provide these materials during the event. *Make Your School* also provides the material for the prototypes to the participating schools. Besides different circuit boards and sensors (e.g. Arduino, Lego Mindstorm), which are in the material

cases, there is a budget (approx. € 600) for additional purchases. Make Your School pays even catering and eventual travel costs for experts. In the case of *Jugend hackt*, the project team also covers all costs. In addition, there is the special feature that the children stay overnight at the event location - this allows them to devote themselves entirely to the project and network with other young people who have the same interests. All materials required during the prototyping phase are available. In addition to various (programmable) tools, *Jugend hackt* also has the special feature that it works with open data. By providing this (often unpublished) data, new (local and regional) problems can be identified that can lead to creative social innovations.

The formats differ greatly in duration. For example, *Baut eure Zukunft* can be completed in 6 hours, *Jugend hackt* plans three days for its events. It should be mentioned that depending on the number of children, different resources are needed. On the one hand, you need a venue, (digital) materials and teachers or mentors for the implementation. The resources available play an important role in the length of the event. If there is a lot of support and resources, the formats can be offered longer and either more children can be reached or the existing group can work longer and more intensively on the topics.

Although the results of the projects differ in development and functionality, they all have the same goal: the idea developed - the social innovation that is to improve the world or one's own environment - should be recognizable and conceivable. All formats conclude with a (public) presentation of the ideas and prototypes. How mature the functionality is differs: At *Jugend hackt*, executable software or hardware hack or at least a prototype should be presented. *WILMA* and *Make Your School* make sure that the functionality of the prototypes is recognizable and *Baut Eure Zukunft* is also satisfied with a description or a paper prototype (e.g. for an app).

4.2 Outlook and implications for DOIT

The DOIT programme as framework for DOIT activities and materials was developed already before the case studies analysis. Similar to the existing approaches, the DOIT programme is a combination of Murray's social innovation spiral (Murray et al., 2010), maker education principles (co-design) as well as from early entrepreneurship education. Although the DOIT programme does not directly refer to it, design thinking methodologies are inherently implemented as well.

Figure 2: Overview over the DOIT programme

Source: Schön et al., 2017, Hornung-Prähäuser et al., 2018

Discussing the results of the presented case analysis we see the following issues as relevant for DOIT's further development:

- Although abstract challenges such as the UN's sustainable development goals delivers concrete ideas and prototypes of products, already within the youngest age rank (see case WILMA).
- Besides digital tools and coding, open data should be consequently taken into account for the activities (see case Jugend hackt).
- Especially while developing social innovations within their direct surrounding, e.g. the school, children are highly motivated and might be able to reach not only prototypes, but implemented products (see Make your school).
- Additionally, especially the implementation in school settings could also initiate social innovation in the sense of organizational learning if the school community recognizes the children's work and their impact.

In general, DOIT aims to present several diverse activities under the above sketched framework (DOIT programme, see Figure 2) within "toolboxes" which might of course include the presented projects and their materials as well.

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